

SEEKING THE MAN IN THE OBJECT: VIRILITY, POWER AND PHALLIC APPROPRIATION IN ART.

PROCURAR O HOMEM NO OBJETO: VIRILIDADE, PODER E APROPRIAÇÃO FÁLICA NA ARTE.

À LA RECHERCHE DE L'HOMME DANS L'OBJET : VIRILITÉ, POUVOIR ET APPROPRIATION PHALLIQUE DANS L'ART.

BUSCANDO AL HOMBRE EN EL OBJETO: VIRILIDAD, PODER Y APROPIACIÓN FÁLICA EN EL ARTE.

Francisca Sousa

Faculty of Fine Arts, University of Porto; i2ADS – Research Institute in Art, Design and Society, Portugal

ABSTRACT: This article is an analysis of virility as a historical and symbolic construction, deeply rooted in power mechanisms that articulate notions of masculinity, authority, and sexual dominance. Through a brief critical reading of Western visual culture—from Classical Antiquity to political modernity—it examines how the phallus is established as an emblem of the sovereignty and hierarchization of genders. In dialogue with feminist theory and Paul B. Preciado's Countersexual Manifesto, this study proposes a reading of the prosthesis and the fragmented body as strategies to deconstruct normative masculinity. Finally, this analysis focuses on the work of Louise Bourgeois, whose poetic appropriation of the phallus subverts the patriarchal logic of virile power, reinscribing it within a regime of vulnerability and ambiguity. It argues that contemporary art can operate as a critical space for the symbolic redistribution of power and the reinvention of gender identities.

Keywords: virility, power, art history & visual culture, Louise Bourgeois, contemporary art, feminist theory.

RESUMO: Este artigo convida à análise da virilidade enquanto construção histórica e simbólica, profundamente enraizada em dispositivos de poder que articulam noções de masculinidade, de autoridade e domínio sexual. A partir de uma breve leitura crítica da cultura visual ocidental — da Antiguidade Clássica à modernidade política — examina-se o modo como o falo se instituiu como emblema de soberania e hierarquização dos géneros. Em diálogo com a teoria feminista e com o Manifesto Contra-sexual de Paul B. Preciado, este estudo propõe a leitura da prótese e do corpo fragmentado enquanto estratégias de desconstrução da masculinidade normativa. A análise centra-se, por fim, na obra de Louise Bourgeois, cuja apropriação poética do falo subverte a lógica patriarcal do poder viril, reinscrevendo-o num regime de vulnerabilidade e ambiguidade. Defende-se que a arte contemporânea pode operar como espaço crítico de redistribuição simbólica do poder e de reinvenção das identidades de género.

Palavras-chave: virilidade, poder, teoria sexual, Louise Bourgeois, arte contemporânea

RÉSUMÉ: Cet article propose une analyse de la virilité comme construction historique et symbolique, profondément ancrée dans les mécanismes de pouvoir qui articulent les notions de masculinité, d'autorité et de domination sexuelle. À travers une brève lecture critique de la culture visuelle occidentale – de l'Antiquité classique à la modernité politique –, il examine comment le phallus s'est imposé comme emblème de souveraineté et de hiérarchisation des genres. En dialogue avec la théorie féministe et le Manifeste Contre-sexuel de Paul B. Preciado, cette étude propose une lecture de la prothèse et du corps fragmenté comme stratégies de déconstruction de la masculinité normative. Enfin, l'analyse se concentre sur l'œuvre de Louise Bourgeois, dont l'appropriation poétique du phallus subvertit la logique patriarcale du pouvoir viril, la

réinscrivant dans un régime de vulnérabilité et d'ambiguïté. L'article soutient que l'art contemporain peut constituer un espace critique pour la redistribution symbolique du pouvoir et la réinvention des identités de genre.

Mots-clés: virilité, pouvoir, théorie sexuelle, Louise Bourgeois, art contemporain

RESUMEN: Este artículo invita a analizar la virilidad como una construcción histórica y simbólica, profundamente arraigada en los mecanismos de poder que articulan nociones de masculinidad, autoridad y dominio sexual. A través de una breve lectura crítica de la cultura visual occidental —desde la Antigüedad Clásica hasta la modernidad política—, examina cómo el falo se consolidó como emblema de soberanía y jerarquización de géneros. En diálogo con la teoría feminista y el Manifiesto Contrasexual de Paul B. Preciado, este estudio propone una lectura de la prótesis y el cuerpo fragmentado como estrategias para deconstruir la masculinidad normativa. Finalmente, el análisis se centra en la obra de Louise Bourgeois, cuya apropiación poética del falo subvierte la lógica patriarcal del poder viril, reinscribiéndola en un régimen de vulnerabilidad y ambigüedad. Argumenta que el arte contemporáneo puede operar como un espacio crítico para la redistribución simbólica del poder y la reinención de las identidades de género.

Palabras-clave: virilidad, poder, teoría sexual, Louise Bourgeois, arte contemporáneo

1. Introduction

Virility has historically functioned as a symbolic dispositif of power, structuring normative models of masculinity associated with strength, moral authority, and sexual domination. Rooted in Western and Christian patriarchal traditions, this conception produced hierarchical distinctions between genders, legitimizing the subordination of women and the exclusion of dissident bodies. As the anthropologist and feminist activist Françoise Héritier (2005) observes, masculine domination has persisted in both visible and insidious forms, shaping the social construction of sexual identity.

This article proposes a critical reading of this symbolic legacy by examining the centrality of the phallus as an emblem of power and analyzing contemporary artistic strategies aimed at its deconstruction. Drawing on the notions of prosthesis and the fragmented body, the study identifies the work of Louise Bourgeois as a paradigmatic case of phallic appropriation and the subversion of normative virility.

2. Virility, Power, and Exclusion

Of patriarchal origin, virility has been associated with the celebration of the strong male body and established as a symbolic measure of authority and hegemony in Western cultural models. The idolization of the athletic male body in Greco-Roman culture and the valorization of military command were historically sustained by ideals of courage

and discipline that permeated both political and civic life. Classical sculpture, vase painting, and mural painting presented an unashamed masculine nudity that set aesthetic canons considered universal¹. From posture to mathematical harmony, these normative models defined virility as the antithesis of traits culturally associated with femininity.

As historian Georges Vigarello argues, the narrative surrounding women was constructed through the systematic devaluation of their qualities within the dominant masculine imaginary. Masculinity was affirmed less through positive self-definition than through the negation of the feminine, a process that transformed virility into a powerful mechanism of exclusion:

The (Greek) texts that extol male superiority are more dedicated to denigrating the feminine than to positively exalting masculinity. It's true that genders are constructed in relation to one another, but the discourse of devaluing women proves easier to have and develop than the construction of a model of virility based on positive masculine values. (Vigarello, 2018: 51).

This oppositional structure persisted across centuries, reappearing in figures such as the invincible superhero of twentieth-century popular culture or the soldier who offers his body to the nation. During the nineteenth century, virility became increasingly associated with military values and warfare, reinforced by the phallic imagery of weapons, the rigidity of uniforms, and the disciplined aesthetics of propaganda—particularly under authoritarian regimes. In the context of the First World War, masculine identity was defined by courage in combat and mastery over fear, a model later intensified by fascist ideologies.

As Johann Chapoutot notes, fascist masculinity is constructed through exclusion: in order to distinguish himself from the feminine, the foreign, and the vulnerable, the fascist man cultivates virility through combat. These discourses, though historically situated, continue to echo in contemporary political rhetoric that reasserts rigid gender roles and hierarchical social orders.

The fascist and Nazi man, therefore, excludes. To distinguish himself from the feminine, the ugly, the alien, he cultivates his virility by fighting. The entire fascist and Nazi imaginary shows this: man fights against himself, against matter, against the other. (Chapoutot, 2011: 302).

Within this logic of power, sexual performance emerged as a central expression of virility. The erect phallus was historically understood as a sign of vitality, sovereignty, and excellence, granting the male genital organ the status of a virile emblem. Phallic

¹ It reflects a Eurocentric view of the body and beauty, not a global aesthetic experience.

symbolism—visible in representations of Priapus, Dionysian processions, and monarchical scepters—functioned for centuries as a metaphor legitimizing male power and the hierarchization of the sexes.

Art historian Caroline Vout demonstrates that in Greco-Roman visual culture, the display of sexual attributes encoded gender, social status, and authority. Yet, as Vout observes, phallic culture contains an implicit warning: excessive machismo risks reducing man to a caricature of his own force, a penis.

Image 1: Detail of a tea pot. Painter of Nikosthenes, ceramics, 30 x 11 cm.

The British Museum.

3. Prosthesis, Countersexuality, and the Fragmented Body

Paul B. Preciado's *Countersexual Manifesto* provides a critical displacement of this paradigm by asserting that gender is prosthetic and technologically produced. By proposing the dildo as the symbolic origin of the penis (Preciado, 2000), Preciado dissolves the notion of sexual difference as a natural given and exposes masculinity as a cultural construction sustained by symbolic technologies of power.

Gender is not purely performative. Gender is first and foremost prosthetic. That is, it occurs in the materiality of the body. It is entirely constructed and, at the same time, purely organic. Gender resembles a dildo. Both go beyond imitation. (Preciado, 2000:65)

By shifting the symbolic power from the male genitalia to the prosthesis - such as the dildo, a central figure in the counter-sexuality formulated by Paul B. Preciado - the idea that sexual difference is a fixed and natural given dissolves. The prosthesis reveals its own artificial condition and, in doing so, exposes the cultural construction of masculinity, dismantling the authority that for centuries has been attributed to the

biological phallus. Thus, the dildo is not merely a substitute: it is a counter-sexual device that denounces the normative fiction of gender, subverts the hierarchies that structure the heteronormative regime, and reinvents the notions of function and pleasure. What could be read as fragmentation becomes multiplicity; what seemed like absence transforms into creative power. In artistic practice, this shift allows us to imagine bodies that are not organized by the logic of lack, but by expansion, experimentation, and the exercise of radical somatic autonomy.

Within contemporary art, bodily fragmentation and prosthesis emerge as strategies of resistance. Fragmentation—once associated with violence or mutilation—becomes a gesture of identity reconfiguration. Artists such as Rebecca Horn, Sin Wai Kin, and Louise Bourgeois explore extensions, silicone accessories, and sculptural dismemberments that challenge the idea of a unified, naturalized body. The prosthesis thus functions as a bodily extension that reveals identity as mutable, transforming lack into creative potency and enabling the imagination of bodies organized by expansion rather than absence.

4. Vulnerability and the Poetic Phallus

Louise Bourgeois's work occupies a singular position within this framework. Beginning her artistic career in the 1940s, Bourgeois appropriated the phallus—traditionally a symbol of patriarchal authority—and transformed it into an ambiguous, vulnerable, and poetic object. In her sculptures, phallic forms merge with other bodily elements, lose rigidity, and assume unstable configurations, becoming simultaneously protective and threatening.

Bourgeois domesticates, absorbs, and reconstructs the phallus, converting it into an element of defense – transforming himself into it and protecting himself. This phallic form populates his sculptures and installations; it metamorphoses with other elements and body parts (merging with breasts, cocoons, and assuming animalistic configurations), granting them strength. In the famous portrait by Robert Mapplethorpe, Bourgeois carries his work *Fillette* (1968) under her arm, positioning herself as its master, in a radical inversion of roles that dialogues with the history of the representation of power. As art critic Donald Kuspit observes, this appropriation does not reaffirm virility, but exposes its structural fragility, transforming the ultimate sign of male domination into an instrument of introspection and subversion:

She says she's afraid of it, but she doesn't look fearful in the photograph. She triumphs over the phallus, completely and unequivocally dominating it. Bourgeois loves her power over it - the power of handling it, of feeling its firmness and

erectness, even making it erect and firm (...). It is her slave, and she is its absolute master. (Kuspit, 2008)

Image 2: Portrait of Louise Bourgeois with Fillette. Robert Mapplethorpe, photograph, 40 x 40 cm, 1982.

Robert Mapplethorpe Foundation.

This logic is further developed in *The Destruction of the Father* (1974), an installation that stages a visceral scenario in which the paternal figure—symbol of law and authority—is reduced to fragmented, consumable matter. Through organic, grotesque forms reminiscent of a sacrificial banquet, Bourgeois enacts the symbolic dismantling of the phallus as an instance of power. Authority is no longer centralized but dispersed across fragments, anticipating a post-phallic, prosthetic logic in which power becomes unstable and relational.

Along with Paul B. Preciado's *Countersexual Manifesto*, *The Destruction of the Father* or even her sculpture *The Sleep II* (1967) can be understood as an anticipation of this prosthetic and post-phallic logic. Power no longer resides in a central organ, but is dispersed into fragments, objects, and extensions. The phallus ceases to be the origin and becomes residue. As in countersexuality, sexual difference ceases to be a natural given and transforms into a field of material and symbolic experimentation.

Image 3: The Destruction of the Father. Louise Bourgeois, installation, 1974.
Glenstone Museum

Image 4: The Sleep II. Louise Bourgeois, marble and wood, 60 x 80 cm, 1967.
Glenstone Museum

5. Conclusion

This article has demonstrated that virility is not a natural essence but a historical construction sustained by symbolic regimes of power, exclusion, and bodily hierarchy. The phallus, as its central emblem, long functioned as a technology for legitimizing masculine sovereignty and regulating desire.

The emergence of prosthesis and bodily fragmentation in contemporary theory and art destabilizes this centrality by revealing the fictional foundations of normative

masculinity. In Louise Bourgeois's work, phallic appropriation acquires a singular poetic force: by reinscribing the phallus within vulnerability, ambiguity, and care, Bourgeois dismantles its hegemonic authority and reconfigures it as a mutable object of affect and memory.

Seeking the man in the object thus becomes a critical gesture that exposes the limits of virile power and affirms contemporary art as a privileged site for reimagining the body, gender, and desire.

BIBLIOGRAPHIC REFERENCES

- Bourgeois, Louise, Bernadac, Marie, & Obrist, Hans-Ulrich. (1998). *Destruction of the father, reconstruction of the father: writings and interviews, 1923-1997*, MIT Press.
- Courtine, Jean-Jacques (dir.)(2011), *História da Virilidade 3 - A Virilidade Em Crise? Séculos XX-XXI*, Lisboa:Orfeu Negro, 2022.
- Héritier, Françoise (2005), *Hommes, femmes : la construction de la différence*, Paris: Le Pommier / Cité des sciences et de l'industrie.
- Hessel, Katy (2024), *A História da Arte sem Homens*, Objectiva.
- Hooks, Bell (1984), *Teoria Feminista: Da Margem ao Centro*, Lisboa: Orfeu Negro, 2020.
- Joseph-Lowery, Frédérique (2010), *Through the Eye of a Needle*. Disponível em: <http://www.artnet.com/magazineus/features/lowery/louise-bourgeois6-15-10.asp>. Acedido em 29/12/2025.
- Kuspit, Donald (2008), *The Phallic Woman*. Disponível em: <http://www.artnet.com/magazineus/features/kuspit/bourgeois-the-phallic-woman11-3-10.asp>. Acedido em 29/12/2025.
- Miller, Juliet (2008), *Power and vulnerability in the work of Louise Bourgeois" in The Creative Feminine and her Discontents*, London: Routledge.
- Preciado, Paul B. (2000), *Manifesto Contra-Sexual*, Lisboa: Orfeu Negro, 2019.
- Vigarello, Georges (dir.) (200), *História da Virilidade 1 - A Invenção da Virilidade: Da Antiguidade às Luzes*, Lisboa:Orfeu Negro, 2018.
- Vout, Caroline (2013), *Sex on Show: Seeing the Erotic in Greece and Rome*, London: The British Museum Press.

Autor: Francisca Sousa (1992), born in Viseu, lives and works in Porto. She holds a degree in Fine Arts from the Faculty of Fine Arts of the University of Porto, completed a study program in London at Central Saint Martins, and holds a master's degree in Multimedia Art from the Faculty of Fine Arts of the University of Lisbon. Her artistic practice is part of a unique universe, where painting, illustration, and performance disentangle the body and modesty in portraits that explore the peculiarly subtle lines of the erotic universe, equally transversal to purity and violence. She is a PhD researcher at i2ADS - Research Unit in Art and Design, University of Porto.

Email: franciscasio@gmail.com